

The Rights Of The Public Inlight Of The Shariah And The Legal

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Abstract

Islamic law has developed an integrated and accurate approach to controlling and regulating the behavior of individuals in general within the group, it is a general and comprehensive law and valid for all time and place, and within the scope of the comprehensiveness characterized by Islamic law, we find that it was interested in the public function and its employees and considered it a responsibility and honesty to serve the citizen and society governed and directed its religious law at the beginning, so we find that Islamic law was keen to establish standards and rules of legitimacy governing the ethics and ethics of the public service, Where the idea of a job in Islam is based on a religious duty, and it is known that the public servant is a member of the Muslim community, and adheres to what everyone is committed to, but since he has a status in taking over a matter of general Muslims, it has rights and duties that exceed what the rest of Muslims, and these rights seem clear in the Holy Quran and the Prophet's Sunnah, and in return we find legislation governing the civil service in contemporary countries keen to consolidate the concept of employee rights, In order to ensure the regular functioning of public facilities and to create confidence and appreciation among citizens and recipients of the public service in the work of the State, and to adopt a state of respect and appreciation for its role in providing services in the best possible way to citizens and society alike.

Introduction

Thus, States have sought to reflect the rights and obligations of the public servant by enacting various laws and regulations that clarify everything surrounding the public service and the public servant so that it is clear, stable and unified in all posts, except those whose members require special legislation.

Study problem:

The problem of the study is summarized in the rights of the public employee between reality and the law from the perspective of Islamic jurisprudence, where Islamic law and man-made laws agreed that the public employee has rights that must be performed by the employer, which is the state or the government, and therefore these rights differed from one state to another. According to the nature of this state, the problem of the study resulted in the main question: What are the rights of the public employee in the light of Islamic Sharia and the law? Several sub-questions are derived from the main question, which are:

- 1- What is the concept of the public servant in Islamic Sharia and law?
- 2- What are the rights of the public employee in Islamic Sharia and law?

Objectives of the study:

- 1- Explanation of the concept of the public servant in Islamic Sharia and law.
- 2- Clarifying the rights of the public employee in Islamic Sharia and law

Study objectives:

- 1- Explaining the concept of the public servant in Islamic law and law
- 2- Clarifying the rights of the public servant in Islamic law andlaw.

The importance of the study:

The importance of the study stems from the fact that it carries with it an important subject in itself and its nature. The public employee is one of the most important tools of the state that must be taken care of and given all his rights to be able to give. The study also seeks to clarify what was stated in Islamic Sharia regarding the rights of the public employee and what the positive legislator decided In this regard, which adds new dimensions in the legal rooting and systematic analysis of the issue of employee rights.

Curriculum:

The researcher relied on the descriptive analytical method by referring to the sources of Islamic law and scientific and jurisprudential references from books, studies, research, periodicals and analysis to highlight the problem of the study. Comparison from the perspective of Islamic law

Study plan:

The first topic: the concept of the public servant in Islamic Sharia and law.

The first requirement: the concept of the public servant in Islamic law.

The second requirement: the concept of the public servant in positive law.

The second topic: the rights of the public employee in Islamic Sharia.

The first requirement: the rights of the public employee in Islamic law.

The second requirement: the rights of the public servant in positive law.

Results and recommendations.**The first topic: the concept of the public servant in Islamic law and law****Boot and split:**

As is known in administrative jurisprudence that the idea of the public servant is generally related to the state, the employee works in the service of the state and therefore, the public servant, although the names differ in different regulations and legislation, and in various eras, whether in the past or the present, the public servant was not born of the modern era, in the past Islamic law knew the public servant and the job - the public mandate as in the term of Islamic jurisprudence that he occupies, Which was based on the basic idea of being a specific social service power for a certain wage and we will shed more light on the following demands:

The first requirement: the concept of the public servant in Islamic law.

The second requirement: the concept of the public servant in positive law.

Demand 1: The concept of the public servant in Islamic law

The worker is considered the "public servant" in the Islamic State as the basis of administrative work, he is the one who implements the system and issues decisions, and speaks on behalf of the administration and in turn expresses its will and exercises the services required by the facility, which is the honest guard and the tool of the state and its true appearance, and people see the state and the government through it.

In the studies of the Prophetic Sunnah, there are indications that determine the knowledge of Islamic law for the idea of the public servant and determining his capacity, as it came in the hadith on the authority of Uday bin Umayra, may God be pleased with him, who said: I heard the Messenger of God, peace be upon him, say: He was arrogance that he would bring on the Day of Resurrection, so a black man from the Ansar said, "As if I am looking at him." He said: "Oh, Messenger of God, accept your work for me." He said, "Malik." He said, "I heard you say such and such." He said, "And I am saying now: "What we have appointed from you for a deed, let him bring a little and a lot of it. He took and what he forbade is over."

This is evidenced by the fact that the employee is the worker and that the word we used was stated in general, to indicate that the worker is in all state facilities and affairs, as well as the talk to the secretariat of the public service and the need not to violate its duties categorically.

Nor did Islamic law call him a public servant, but rather called him a worker for the incumbent, and the worker's recipe includes the caliph, the governors of the princes, the accountants and others, all of which indicate the status of the public servant at the moment.

Although Islamic law has defined the public servant, Islamic jurisprudence has not defined it and has not clearly mentioned its concept, and did not use this term to denote the occupant of the public service, but it was called many names including: employers of public functions, workers, servants, employees, diwans, diwan owners, especially the king, entourage, the breadth, soldiers, companions, guardians of the state, state agents, the excluded, and others.

The public servant of the contemporary Islamic system was also defined as: "Everything imitated by the imam or his deputy in accordance with the interests of the nation, or anyone who works for the state, one of its institutions or public bodies."

Based on the above, Islamic law defined the idea of a public official and was nicknamed several titles according to the functions he held, and he was nicknamed the caliph, imam, guardian, judge, calculated, worker, or other names, these were public officials, although they were not called in the terms, and some have known the public servant in Islamic jurisprudence as: "The person who works for the state, and a decision is issued by the competent authority to assign the job to him."

According to the researcher: The definitions differed in Islamic law and jurisprudence as well as contemporary jurists of the concept of public servant, but all definitions tended to be that the public official is the person who holds a position concerned with the interests of the state by the imam or his deputy, and this employee does his work that leads to the realization of the interests of society through public institutions and bodies of the state.

Requirement 2: The concept of the public servant in positive law

The definitions and concepts of the public servant differed from state to state, depending on the difference of public functions themselves for states, and the importance they give them, the public function in each particular country is the result of the development of a history experienced by the state influenced by a set of different factors such as the geographical location and economic and social level of that country, and the political system prevailing in it, and the evolving nature of administrative law makes it difficult to define the public servant for a long period of time within the same state, Therefore, there is no unified definition of the public official in the branches of general laws civil, criminal, constitutional and administrative, because the legislator in the majority of countries is always reluctant to give an all-encompassing definition that prevents the public official and limits his efforts to introducing some communities of employees when they are exposed to some of their affairs by organizing, throwing that task on the shoulders of jurisprudence and the judiciary.

It can be said that there are several definitions of the public servant in positive law, and these definitions vary by country, including:

1- The definition of the French administrative judiciary/ defined by the French administrative judiciary as: "Every person employed by the administration within the scope of common law and contributes to public activity".

2- The staff member was defined as: "Every person who holds a permanent position in a state-run public facility through direct exploitation, and this definition contains two elements agreed upon by the judiciary and the judiciary and have concluded with the functional legislation:

- The permanent occupation of a permanent job and the lesson here is the permanence of the job and not the employee.

- Service in a state-run public facility in a direct exploitation manner, so that an employee is not the person who works in a facility that is not directly state-run, but is managed by concessional, mixed economy or otherwise.

In the Egyptian judiciary, the public servant was defined by the Administrative Supreme Court as: "Who is entrusted with permanent work in the service of a state-run public facility or another common law person by holding a position within the administrative organization of that facility, and the court stipulated that the person should be considered a public official with three conditions:

- Contribute to the work of a state-run public facility or central, local or attached administrative authority.

- The contribution should be permanent, i.e. the job should be permanent.

- The job must have been filled by appointment.

In Egyptian legislation, the Egyptian legislator did not define the public official in any of the successive public service laws, but merely enumerated the categories to which these laws apply and apply to them, and the Egyptian legislator continued to do so even in the current civil service law of 2015.

The public servant also means: "A person appointed by a competent body to fill a position included in the civil service formation system in parallel with a government department, whatever the nature or so-called nature of that post."

According to the researcher: the definition of the employee as the person who is appointed by the state in an institution or body of its government bodies and institutions, and this position is included in the public functions based on the budget of the government or the state.

The second topic: the rights of the public servant in Islamic law

Booting and splitting:

In order for the public servant to carry out the duties assigned to him by the administration to the fullest, he must have the rights to perform his duty and function and he is assured of his livelihood and that of his family, and is assured that he receives incentives and breaks that enable him to regain his activity and renew his abilities, as well as his right to promotion when proving merit, where some rights to be given to the employee will be studied from the perspective of Islamic law:

1- **Salary: Where he represents the first and most important right of the worker** after taking office, he is the direct reason for his entry into service, so Islam took great care of him, and he says: "He said that I want to give you one of my daughters to make eight arguments." (Stories, verse 26). The Prophet said: "Give the wage earner before his sweat dries up."

These texts emphasize the need to give the worker his wages as long as he has taken up work by the competent authority, which must impose the wage in exchange for the service he performs to this authority for this wage, and that the wage is limited and sufficient for his or her life.

2- **Bonuses:** Where Islam defined the allowances and applied them in the lives of Muslims, Omar ibn al-Khattab, may God bless him, increased the salaries of his workers annually with the increase of state resources, he imposed to his judge a salary of 100 dirhams per month, and this salary remained in increase until it reached 500 dirhams under Ali bin Abi Talib, and he expressed his competence by saying: "He met them and fulfilled them."

3- Rewards: Where Islamic history knew this kind of reward, Omar wrote to Abu Musa al-Ashari, may God bless him, a book in which he wrote: "I have sent you with The Angry Son of Samra al-Amberi in newspapers, if I come to you like this and so on, and give him 200 dirhams, and if he comes to you afterwards, do not give him anything and write to me any day he presented to you."

4- **The right to leave:** In order for the worker to perform his work with dedication and sincerity, he must rest from work in which he regains his physical, mental and psychological activity, as indicated by the rest of the body, body and soul, so there is no continuous stress that affects them mentally and physically. The Prophet (pbuh) acknowledged Salman's statement to Abu Zar, may God bless them, when he denied stressing himself and concern for his family by saying: "God has a right on you, for your family truly, and for your family for you, and for your people, and for your people, he gave everyone his right, and the Prophet said: "Believe Salman."

5- The right to grievance: This right is one of the most important rights that an employee must receive, because through it he is described to himself and rests himself by taking her right, and this is the justice of Allah almighty in the land, and that the Prophet (pbuh) is the fairest of the oppressed, whether he is one of his workers or other members of his society, and the Islamic State has known this right under the name of the "state of grievances", which means: "The complainants went to the fairness of awe and the disputants of the unjust with prestige." "The Ombudsman receives complaints and grievances from employees because he is an observer of the administrative bodies, which means that the administrative thought of Islam takes the second form of surveillance, namely, the existence of an independent body that conducts the investigation, oversight and complaints of staff."

6- **The right to retire:** Pension is one of the most important advantages of the public service, and one of the factors that encourages individual employees to join it because of the stability it provides in the life of the employee and his family after him, and with this right the work of sharia jurists, as they agreed to retain the tender for those who are old or unable to work for a while, as granted to his family, who support their salary and adequate livelihood at the time of his death, The Prophet (pbuh) was entrusting all those who did not take the interests of themselves from the descendants of young needy children and children from whom their father died, as well as patients who could not work as much as they did in their own countries, as stipulated in Islamic law.

According to the above: the public servant enjoys many of the benefits and rights guaranteed to him by Islamic law, and these rights cannot be overlooked, such as salary, allowances, incentives, various vacations such as sick, maternal, study and other leave, and we will shed more details in the following demands:

The first requirement: the rights of the public servant in Islamic law.

The second requirement: the rights of the public servant in positive law.

Demand 1: The rights of the public servant in Islamic law

Muslim jurists have called the term "public mandate" an expression of the functions of the supreme state, including the position of caliphate, the head of state, which is the highest and highest job in the Islamic State, and the system of public jurisdiction or public function in Islam is based on the basic idea of being a social service defined by authority for a certain wage; That's a glorl." Islam also preserves the right to promotion if it is better and more serious, and there is its right to leave, for the Prophet (PBUH) said: "Go away from hearts for an hour, then the hearts will be blinded if they are blinded." Islam also guaranteed the employee's right to promotional leave and other rights.

In positive law, if there are a number of duties on the part of the employee that is necessary to abide by and abide by, the rules of justice require that there be a range of rights and privileges, because violating the principle of balancing rights and duties will negatively affect logic while performing his or her duties and finally this will harm society and that it is based on each citizen performing his duty towards him in full while ensuring that society The citizen has his rights and freedoms.

Thus, the State and the administration can operate and continue only by its employees, and management in all states is equal to the equals of its employees who represent it and act on its behalf, and as a result the employee has become a very important role as the implementer of state policy and entrusted with the functions of performing the basic services of citizens. The staff member is responsible for the administration of justice, the maintenance of public order and the continued provision of service to citizens. The employee has an importance in the management of public facilities, and therefore a dangerous role in bringing life to life in its social and economic fields, and given the importance of the public servant's message, states have taken him with special care, and have developed his own laws and regulations governing the methods of selection, appointment, promotion and other affairs until the end of his relationship with the public service.

With the recent development, the performance of the public servant declined, and he was deprived of many of his rights guaranteed by Islamic law, and even the positive law applied on the ground became different from the principles that were formulated and worked through, it spread and spread corruption in Islamic countries, especially developing ones, and the principle of civil service was largely absent, and many Arab and Islamic countries began to suffer from the concept of public service applied by Islamic law, The concepts of lack of

accountability and control appeared on the public servant, and the authority of the large family or the influence of the tribe on the individual and society grew, making it difficult to apply a firm concept of civil service due to the mixing of concepts of civil service with the public interest, and the mixing of family or social considerations with considerations of the public interest, since many employees of the government apparatus are no longer absorbed by the rights of the employee, Their job has become only a source of income, and most of them do not perform their job properly until they get their rights, and another part of them waste important resources in the country and do not direct them properly, and therefore many employees no longer have rights to advocate as a result.

Understanding the individual as explained by Islamic jurisprudence for his role in life and society, and the impact on the public servant in achieving development and obtaining his full rights, is an important factor in applying the concept of public service approved and guaranteed by Islam, which is actually declining as a result of widespread corruption in Islamic countries. It helps to understand the role of sensing responsibility in the conduct of public service, and in the prophet's talk about the responsibility of each individual for his parish, whether husband, wife or boy, for the greatest evidence of the individual responsibility of each person for his parish, while entrusting him with this small responsibility or growing up until the civil service regains its progress after it has recently retreated.

According to the researcher: the concepts of the rights of the

public servant in Islamic jurisprudence, and what is guaranteed by Islamic law has begun to fade in the modern era for many reasons, including corruption that is rampant in many Developing Islamic countries, which reflected on the lack of harmonization of positive laws as a theoretical framework and what is applied to reality in this regard.

Requirement 2: The rights of the public servant in positive law

After the completion of all arrangements relating to the appointment and receipt of the employee to work in the public service in which he was appointed, the employee is subject to administrative laws and regulations relating to the public service, which determine the rights enjoyed by the employee, where the majority of States and laws almost agree on these rights, especially with regard to the employee's access to promotions, salary, allowances, bonuses, pension rights, vacations, etc.

1. Salary and its accessories:The salary means the amount of money that an employee receives monthly for the tasks of his or her job, and all other financial benefits attached to it, such as the additional salary, travel and accommodation allowance, housing allowance and other allowances, are the employee's right to receive the salary, which is the main reason for joining the job often, and for its importance, the legislator has given him special protection. On the one hand, the administrative judiciary in the eyes of disputes relating to salaries received by employees is divided into two types:

Periodic allowances: The employee is granted annually from the beginning of the month following the expiry of one year of the appointment date or the previous annual allowance is granted.

- **Incentive allowance: The legislator authorized the** granting of a bonus to the employee in order to encourage maximum effort at work equivalent to the periodic allowance established for him and the granting of this allowance does not affect the granting of the periodic allowance on its annual date.

2- **Promotion:** Promotion means all changes in the employee's legal status that would provide him or her from his peers, and promotion brings material and moral benefits to the employee, allowing the employee to reach senior positions, thereby fulfilling his ambition to obtain a greater financial degree and more important terms of reference.

3- **Leave:** Since the general principle is that the employee should devote himself to his work and give him all his time, but for the purposes of the common good and the interest of the employee, the public servant must have a number of days off for rest and renew the physical and psychological activity, so leave is one of the functional rights of the public servant, derived from his regular position, which he occupies in a way that does not disturb the continuity of the work and the provision of the public service properly, While leave is an employee's right, it is not an absolute right, but a right when the conditions of its entitlement are met, and the administration has discretion to grant it, not grant it, or specify when it will be granted on certain leave. These holidays vary in:

- **Regular leave:** a leave that is normally decided for the convenience of working and to renew the employee's activity, which reflects on his competence in the performance of his or her job.

- **Maternity leave:** A leave granted to the employed mother, whose purpose is to take care of her child, who is not more than one year old and one year without pay.

- **Pregnancy and childbirth leave:** A leave that the pregnant employee deserves before giving birth and may be repeated whenever pregnancy and childbirth are repeated.

- **Sick leave:** It is important to maintain the health of the public servant so that he can carry out his or her duties to the fullest, so the legislator should have provided the necessary care to the employee by granting him leave if he suffered from a disease that prevents him from doing his job as required.
- **Marital leave:** The wife may be granted leave to accompany her husband, an employee who is in a job or a student of the mission, to complete his studies outside the country, the normal leave she deserves at full salary and beyond that without pay, provided that the wife enjoys this leave once while the husband is in one place.
- **Study leave:** The Arab legislator has authorized in many legislations to grant the employee a full salary scholarship if the employee holds a preliminary or higher university degree and completed two years in an actual job service to complete his studies outside the country and obtain a higher certificate and the duration of the leave is the period required to study and learn the language in accordance with the conditions adopted for the students of the missions.

According to the researcher: It can be said that all positive laws have guaranteed the employee many benefits and rights within its various legislations, and these rights are the right to salary in all its branches such as incentives, allowances and others, as well as various leave such as sick leave, maternity leave or study leave for those who wish to study outside the country and other vacations.

Conclusion

A lot of positive legislation has taken care of the issue of the rights of the public servant, because of its clear and prominent importance, because many of the burdens are placed on the public servant, so that Islamic law and positive laws have guaranteed many of the rights of the public servant such as the right to salaries, allowances, incentives and vacations of all kinds so that the public servant can carry out his duties to the fullest.

The reality today is not related to what exists in the principles of positive laws guaranteed by Islamic jurisprudence, especially since these principles have been realistically changed by the corruption cases that exist in many developing Muslim countries, which has reflected on the rights of the employee significantly and clearly.

Results:

- 1- The rights of the public servant are one of the Islamic controls guaranteed by Islamic jurisprudence and sharia from the time of the Prophet (pbuh) to the present day.
- 2- Many positive laws ensured the rights of the public servant because employees are critical to strengthening the pillars and establishing the rules of the state, especially since they are the backbone of any state and government institutions.
- 3- The reality today is that it is not related to what exists in the principles of positive laws guaranteed by Islamic jurisprudence on the subject of the rights of the public servant, especially since these principles have been realistically changed by the cases of corruption that exist in many Muslim countries.

Therecommendations:

- 1- The principles of Islam should be applied in the subject of public servant rights, especially since Islamic law has established comprehensive, adequate and adequate principles in this subject.
- 2- Many modern legislation must have a large number of legal articles that ensure that the public official has broad rights, which clearly reflects on his performance.
- 3- The study recommends that what is in positive law should be balanced against the rights of the employee and what is applied on the ground, especially if Islamic jurisprudence and sharia are used because they are comprehensive and sufficient for every time and place.

List of references:

First: Arab sources:

- 1- Ibn Saad, Abu Abdullah bin Mene'i al-Basri, Grand Classes, C7, Ihsan Abbas Investigation, Dar Sader, Beirut, 1968: p. 126.
- 2- Ibn Maga The Sinan of Ibn Maga, The Book of Mortgages, The Door of Wage Earners, Hadith 2443, C3.
- 3- Albanian, Mohamed Nasreddine, True Intimidation and Intimidation, C1, Knowledge Library, Riyadh, I5, DT: p. 192.
- 4- Bukhari, Saheed Al-Bukhari, The Book of Fasting, The Door of Who Swore on His Brother to Break The Volunteer: Hadith 1968.

Second: Arabic books

- 1- Hazem Hamdi Al-Jamali, Public Servant and His Duties between Islamic Law and Positive Law Comparative Study, Faculty of Law and Judicial Practice, University of Palestine, Gaza, D.T.: p. 2-3.
- 2- Hamdi Attia Amer, Public Servant's Provisions in Positive and Islamic Law Comparative Study, Law Loyalty Library, i1, 2015: p. 42.
- 5- Al-Ghazali, Abu Hamed, Taber Al-Tabb in The Advice of Kings, Ahmed Shamseddine Investigation, Scientific Book House, Beirut, i1, 1988: p. 78.

- 3- Fathi Fikri, Principles of Public Service, C1, Arab Renaissance Publishing and Distribution House, Cairo, Egypt, i1, 1987: p. 55-56
- 4- Fouad Abdullah Al-Omar, Ethics and Behavior of Public Service Workers and Censorship from an Islamic Perspective, Islamic Institute for Research and Training, King Fahd National Library during publishing, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, i1, 1999: p. 20.
- 5- Fouad Abdel Moneim Ahmed, Principles of Public Administration and Administrative System in Islam, University Youth Foundation, Alexandria, 1991: p. 57.
- 6- Mazen Lilo Radhi, Administrative Law, Arab Academy of Publishing and Distribution, Denmark, i1, 2019: p. 335.
- 6- Al-Mardi, Ali bin Mohammed al-Basri, Royal Provisions and Religious States, Think Tank for Printing, Publishing and Distribution, Cairo, i1, 1983: p. 19 and beyond.
- 7- Mohamed Badran, Administrative Law Public Service, Arab Renaissance Publishing and Distribution House, Cairo, Egypt, 1990: p. 19.
- 8- Mohamed Joudat Al-Malt, Disciplinary Responsibility for the Public, Arab Renaissance Publishing and Distribution House, Cairo, Egypt, 1967: p. 20.
- 9- Mohamed Fouad Muhanna, Egyptian Administrative and Comparative Law, C1, D.N., Cairo, Egypt, 1995: p. 153 and beyond.
- 10- Mansour Al-Atum, Disciplinary Responsibility of the Public Servant Comparative Study of Disciplinary Systems in Syria, Egypt and France, Oriental Press and Library, Amman, Jordan, i1, 1984: p. 18.
- 11- Nawaf Kanaan, Brief in Jordanian Administrative Law, Book II, Orient Horizons House - Publishers, Amman, Jordan, 2012: p. 23.
- 7- Wakqi, Abu Bakr Mohammed bin Hayyan, Judges News, C2, Investigation of Abdelaziz Al-Maraghi, Grand Commercial Library, Egypt, i1, 1947: p. 227.

Third: Scientific messages

- 1- The children of Abdullah Marzouk, the dismissal of the public servant of the Islamic system and contemporary administrative systems, an unpublished master's letter, Al-Azhar University, Cairo, 1999: p. 16.
- 2- Rasha Abdul Razzaq Jassim al-Shammari, Modern Principles of Public Function between Islamic Law and Positive Law Comparative Study, Unpublished PhD, University of Al-Nahrin, Iraq, 2008: p. 71.
- 3- Mubarak Baddah Albaddah, termination of public servant service due to incompetence study comparing Jordanian and Kuwaiti law, unpublished master's thesis, Middle East University, Jordan, 2011: p. 43.
- 4- Mahmoud Mohammed Ma'bara, Administrative Corruption and Its Treatment in Islamic Jurisprudence: A Comparative Study of Jordanian Administrative Law, Unpublished PhD, University of Jordan, Jordan, 2010: p. 41.

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